

BOTANICAL DESCRIPTION, CULTIVATION HISTORY, AND BENEFICIAL PROPERTIES OF BROCCOLI CABBAGE

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Annotation. This article provides information about the origin of broccoli cabbage, the history of its cultivation, its distribution on the world scale, and its beneficial properties for the human body.

Key words. Broccoli, sulforaphane, lyzin, isoleucine, methionine, choline, vitamin.

Introduction. The earliest information about broccoli cabbage was found in French treatises titled *Historia Generalis Plantarum* (1587). It originated in the 6th–5th centuries BC through crossbreeding with other cabbage varieties. (<https://bio.urgau.ru/images/1-2023/5-1-2023.pdf>) Broccoli's homeland is southern Italy, where this crop has been cultivated for 2,000 years (T. Biggs, 1986). It began to be cultivated in Ancient Rome and was called Pompeii cabbage (<http://www.1001recept.com/health/brokkol>). From there it was brought to Byzantium and later spread throughout the world (<http://www://zemledelye.ru/index.php/owoszi/kapusta/>).

MAIN PART. This variety of cabbage was brought to France in the 16th century and to England in the early 18th century. In the 1920s, Italian migrants brought broccoli cabbage to the United States and began cultivating it in San Jose. In 1926, the first shipment of broccoli seeds arrived on the East Coast, and since then California has become the largest broccoli-producing state in the United States, and today it is the leading producer. to Boston, on the East Coast, and since then, California has become the largest broccoli-producing state in the U.S., accounting for 90% of the total domestic production today (Broccoli Production (Ag Alternatives)).

According to A. A. Autko and A. A. Autko (2008), broccoli was brought to Germany in the 18th century. Although it was later introduced from there to Russia, it did not become widely popular until the early 20th century. Interest in this crop increased after the Chernobyl nuclear power plant accident because broccoli has the ability to help remove heavy metals from the human body and its products can effectively treat radiation diseases. Therefore, this type of cabbage is considered beneficial in regions with unfavorable environmental conditions.

Although broccoli is considered a less common, non-traditional vegetable crop in our country, demand for it has been increasing in recent years. In particular, export volume is growing at a rapid pace. In 2021, 6,000 tons of broccoli were exported to the Russian Federation, which was twice the amount compared to 2020 (<https://www.agro.uz/ru/22-0035/>).

Broccoli is an annual, cross-pollinated plant. The leaves are long-petiolate, lyre-shaped, with wavy margins. The plant forms a thick, fleshy stem that grows to a height of 40-70 cm. The central stem terminates in a head of broccoli, which is a cluster of florets and tender side shoots. The head weighs 100-600 g. The head resembles cauliflower in shape, but its color varies: green, bluish, purple, and white. After blooming, the head begins to break apart into flower clusters within 8-10 days, and it loses its commercial appearance.

Broccoli is similar to cabbage and cauliflower in its root characteristics. After the seeds are planted, it forms roots and then side roots. Typically, crown roots form when the main root is damaged during planting. The thickness of the formed roots ranges from 0.5 to 1.0 cm. After a short time, the roots reach a depth of 1.5-2.0 m, and the majority of the roots develop in the top 20-30 cm of soil.

The broccoli stalk differs from that of cabbage and cauliflower. The stem can be 30-50 cm long. The leaves on the stalk are alternate. The stalk terminates in immature, green, main florets (buds). When the main flower head is cut, secondary flowers are produced from the leaf axils. The green flower buds emerging from the leaf axils are smaller in diameter than the main flower buds. When cut at the head, the plant will not produce more heads from the leaf axils, but when cut at the broccoli crown, the plant will produce side shoots.

Broccoli leaves are stalk-like and oval, and in some varieties they may be fragmented. Their color is darker and more bluish-green than that of cabbage and cauliflower.

The immature flower buds, which are considered a vegetable, are also called heads. Although the heads can be light green or purple, green is highly preferred. The heads and flowers resemble those of cauliflower in their morphological characteristics. The size of the main immature flower buds (the head) varies depending on the planting date of the seedlings and seeds and the variety's characteristics. When planted late and with close spacing, the size of the heads decreases. The main heads of broccoli are 5–25 cm in diameter and weigh 100–750 g, while the side shoots are 5–10 cm in diameter and weigh 10–100 g.

Broccoli is a long-day vegetable crop. If the crop is planted late, it flowers early. High and low air temperatures, insufficient moisture in the soil and air, and a lack of nutrients in the soil sharply reduce yield and quality and cause broccoli to flower prematurely. Broccoli flowers are pale yellow and consist of 4 stamens, 4 petals, 6 anthers, and 1 outer organ. The flowers are usually pollinated by bees. The characteristics of the broccoli flower, its method of flowering, and its fertilization biology are very similar to those of cauliflower.

Broccoli heads come in various colors: green, yellow, white, dark orange, and purple (V.I. Likhatsky, 2000).

Broccoli, as with many vegetables in the species *Brassica oleracea*, has a high level of cross-pollination. Therefore, for seed production, it must be grown at a distance of 2000 m from other *Brassica* crops to prevent cross-pollination. If broccoli heads are not harvested in time, they will quickly bolt. For this reason, care must be taken during harvesting, and the plants should be monitored frequently. In broccoli, even after the main head and side shoots have been harvested, flower buds develop from the sides and will bloom to produce seeds.

The fruit is a small cluster. It contains numerous small, round, dark brown or nearly black seeds.

Broccoli varieties differ in the shape of their heads. In early maturing varieties, the central head is typically small and loose. At the same time, side shoots form in the leaf axils. In late maturing varieties, a large and dense central head forms initially. It takes 75-100 days from seedling emergence to head formation. Broccoli is a very willing plant to regrow: after the central head is cut, the side shoots produce new tender produce.

Broccoli contains many beneficial compounds. In particular, its florets contain vitamins B, A, PP, K, and C. In terms of vitamin C content, citrus fruits also take the lead. In addition, broccoli contains many macro- and micronutrients. It is rich in potassium, magnesium, phosphorus, copper, selenium,

manganese, and zinc. The important components of broccoli cabbage listed above help maintain the body's water and electrolyte balance and support the regeneration and growth of cells and tissues.

This type of cabbage contains a large amount of beta-carotene compared to other vegetables, which beautifies the human body, skin, and hair, and prevents aging. Broccoli contains a record amount (up to 6%) of protein compared to other types of cabbage, which contains choline and methionine—substances that help prevent sclerosis.

In terms of the unique amino acids in its protein, broccoli is on par with beef in lysine and isoleucine content, and in terms of tryptophan content, it surpasses egg white. As is well known, plant protein, because it contains no cholesterol at all, is considered much more beneficial for the human body than animal protein. Furthermore, its high content of methionine and choline prevents cholesterol from accumulating in the human body and helps eliminate it from the system. For this reason, patients with cardiovascular diseases are advised to consume broccoli. It helps prevent strokes and heart attacks.

Broccoli cabbage helps the body produce the hormone endorphin due to the unique combination of amino acids in its protein. The hormone endorphin helps improve a person's mood.

The fiber in this vegetable cleanses the gastrointestinal tract and improves the function of the digestive system. The positive effect of broccoli curcumin helps maintain normal insulin levels in the human body.

People who are overweight and want to lose weight should eat more dark green leafy vegetables, including broccoli.

Broccoli and cancer. It is a type of vegetable that is beneficial against stomach ulcers and many other diseases.

Broccoli contains a compound called sulforaphane, which helps produce the NrF2 protein, which has antioxidant properties. Sulforaphane strengthens the cells' protective mechanisms and readies them to combat harmful aggressive factors.

Sulforaphane is especially abundant in young broccoli sprouts. That's why growing broccoli sprouts as microgreens has become popular today. In addition, broccoli sprouts contain sinigrin and I3C, compounds that help the human body fight cancer. Sinigrin inhibits the division and proliferation of cancer cells, destroying them. I3C (indole-3-carbinol) not only combats cancerous tissues but also positively affects the body's immune system, helping to strengthen it and make it capable of fighting cancer.

In conclusion, Broccoli cabbage is a gift of nature for human health, and its ideal balance of vitamins, fiber, mineral salts, and other biologically active substances makes this crop a healthy, diet-friendly product for people of all ages. Furthermore, despite being a relatively uncommon exotic vegetable in our country, broccoli cabbage is seeing growing demand in both domestic and international markets due to the beneficial properties listed above. Therefore, conducting scientific research to develop elements of broccoli cabbage cultivation technology, select cultivar samples suited to our republic's soil and climate conditions, and create new varieties and hybrids is a pressing issue.

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